

On the Marking-tadpole and Marking-shell Ramsey numbers of graphs

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ABSTRACT

Given two graphs G and G_2 , the Ramsey number $R(G, G_2)$ is the smallest integer N such that for any graph G of order N , either G_1 is a subgraph of G , or G_2 is a subgraph of the complement of G . Let C_n denote the cycle of order n and P_k be the path of order k . The Tadpole Graph $T_{n,k}$ is the graph created by concatenating C_n and P_k with an edge from any vertex of C_n to a pendant of P_k for integers $n \geq 3$ and $k \geq 0$. A Shell Graph $S_{n,n-3}$ is a cycle graph with $(n-3)$ chords sharing a common end point called the apex. Defined the **Marking-Tadpole Graph** M_p is a graph derived from Tadpole Graph $T_{n,k}$ where every vertices are adjacent to every vertices of the graph. Moreover, the **Marking-Shell Graph** J_p is a graph originated from Shell Graph where every vertices are adjacent to every vertices of the graph as well. In this study, we show the combinatorial relationships and identities of $R(M_p, C_4)$ to $R(J_p, C_4)$ for every $p \geq 6$ and the subscript $p = n+3$ of M .

Keywords: *marking-tadpole, marking-shell, Ramsey numbers*

I. INTRODUCTION

Marking-Tadpole Graph M_p is a graph derived from Tadpole Graph $T_{n,k}$ where every vertices are adjacent to every vertices of the graph. Moreover, the Marking-Shell Graph J_p is a graph originated from Shell Graph where every vertices are adjacent to every vertices of the graph as well, where the subscript of M is $p = n+1$. This implies that M_p and J_p are complete graphs.

In this study, we consider graphs with complete graphs. For the sake of simplified notations the same with Zhang (2014), we consider a nonempty proper subset $S \subseteq V(G)$ and let $G[S]$ and $G - S$ denote the subgraph induced by S and $V(G) - S$, respectively. Let $N_s(v)$ be the set of all neighbors of a vertex v that are contained in S , let $N_s(v) \cup \{v\}$ and let $d_s(v) = |N_s(v)|$. If $S = V(G)$, we write $N(v) = N_G(v), N[v] = N(v) \cup \{v\}$ and let $d(v) = d_G(v)$. For two vertex-disjoint graphs G_1 and $G_2, G_1 + G_2$ is the graph obtained from $G_1 \cup G_2$

by joining every vertex of G_1 to every vertex of G_2 .

In this study, we denote C_n for a cycle of order n . Moreover, we denote M_p and J_p for Marking-Tadpole and Marking Shell respectively. Like in Zhang (2014), we still use the $\Delta(G), \delta(G)$ and $\alpha(G)$ to denote the maximum degree, the minimum degree and the independence number, respectively, of a graph G .

Given two graphs G_1 and G_2 , the Ramsey number $R(G_1, G_2)$ is the smallest integer N such that for any graph G of order N , either G_1 is a subgraph of G , or G_2 is a subgraph of the complement of G . To deal with the Ramsey Number, the Marking-Tadpole and the Marking-Shell have been developed from Tadpole and Shell respectively, in order to provide the identities and relationship in terms of Ramsey Numbers of Tadpole and Shell.

Below are some facts regarding the Marking-Tadpole and Marking Shell Graphs:

1. C_n and P_k is a subgraph of M_p , where $p = n + k$.
2. M_p is a complete graph.
3. C_n is a subgraph of J_p , where $p \geq n$
4. J_p is a complete graph
5. $K_n \subseteq M_p$

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